

ON THE SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF THE NEW ENLIGHTENERS

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The national awakening that arose in the minds of the most progressive intellectuals of Turkestan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries was clearly visible in the Enlightenment. The Jadids, who were the first heralds of the New Enlightenment, fought with their large-scale practical activities to consolidate and stabilize their ideas in the life of society.

The Jadid movement is one of the periods that left a bright mark on our history. At a time when Turkestan was suffering from colonial oppression in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the Jadid enlighteners entered the arena of struggle. Their main goal was to free the country from colonial oppression and enlighten the people. Before getting acquainted with this movement, it is appropriate to pay attention to the meaning of the word "jadid". This word means "new", "innovation" in Arabic.

In addition to internal factors, there were also external factors in the emergence and formation of the Jadid movement, the most notable of which was the teachings of Ismail Gaspirali. Ismail Gaspirali was born in 1851 near the city of Bakhchisarai in Crimea. He studied in Moscow, later lived in France and Turkey. In 1875–1881, he worked as a teacher in Bakhchisarai and held leadership positions in the government. In an article in the newspaper "Tavrida" in 1881, he expressed his practical program as follows:

- reform the national education system;
- to establish "charitable societies" to financially support the national education system;
- to establish a general national press of the Turkic peoples;
- to liberate Muslim women;
- to create conditions for the training of national specialists and intellectuals[3:30], etc.

Ismail Gaspirali describes the field of education as follows: "The urgent need of the nation is school and enlightenment. Its future depends on school and enlightenment. Or the nation will be doomed, the doomed nation will perish - from lack of schools." He first officially raised this issue in 1881 in his work "Russian Islam". [1:12] Later, Ismail Gaspirali's movement began to spread widely to neighboring regions. This movement also entered Turkestan. At the end of the 19th century, the emergence of new-style schools in Turkestan and

the formation of the national intelligentsia were associated with the activities of Tatar intellectuals and teachers who came from Russia.

The emergence of new-style schools in Turkestan coincided with the years of development of Russian-style schools in the country. Such schools began to be opened by the Tatars in large centers. Academician V.V. Bartold wrote that Tatar schools in these centers were more successful than Russian schools. In Tashkent in 1910, there were 8 Russian-style schools and 16 new-style schools. In Kokand in 1911, there were 2 Russian-style schools with 162 students and 8 new-style schools with 530 students. In his article published in the newspaper "Turkiston" by S. Maksudov, a member of the State Duma, wrote that in 1910 there were 20 new-style schools in Tashkent and 16 in Kokand [1:12].

In the Turkestan Jadidism, the role of such scholars as Mahmudkhodja Behbudiy, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Bobookhun Salimov, Cholpon, Fitrat, Sadridin Ayniy, Sayyid Ahmad Vasliy is significant. The Jadids, overcoming the fierce resistance of the Russian colonialists on the one hand and local ideological opponents on the other, managed to methodologically renew the school system in the region, accelerate the process of literacy and education of the younger generation. The renewal movement was not limited to reforms in the field of education, but also achieved a number of successes in the fields of literature, science, press and printing.

Intellectuals who studied in Kazan at one time, including Ahmadjon Bektemirov, Shokir Mukhtoriy, Shokir Sulaymon, Mukhtor Bakir, Qori Abdurakhmon Taji, Ismail Obidov, and Ghazi Yunus, accomplished great work. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the four-volume "History of Islam" by Shokir Sulayman, the "Comprehensive Geography of Turkestan" by Mukhtar Bakir (who once taught under the Khan of Khiva, Isfandiyor Khan), and a number of beautiful poems by Abdurakhman Taji (his literary pseudonym is "Tikan") [3:39].

Just as the national progressive movement in Central Asia was divided into regions according to its nature, in our country this movement is also divided into the Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva Jadid schools. The development of the progressive movement took place in two stages. In the first stage, this movement, which began as an enlightenment movement, by 1917 turned into its second stage - a political movement.

In the Bukhara Emirate during this period, movements such as the reform of Islamic ideas and the desire to change the madrasah education system began to emerge. In this regard, the services of such prominent Tatar scholars as Abu

Nasr Kursavi (1776–1812) and Shihobiddin Marjani (1818–1889) are particularly commendable. The famous scholar and enlightener Abu Nasr Kursavi was born in 1776 in the city of Kursa, Tatarstan, into a merchant family. He received his early education in the famous madrasah in the village of Machkara, Malmij uyezd. One of his first teachers was Muhammadrahim Yusuf, who said about Kursavi: “I see signs of a true mentor in this boy. If he had been given a long life, he would undoubtedly have become a person of high qualities.” Abu Nasr Kursavi was distinguished by his unique memory and his unwillingness to be satisfied with the superficial answers of his teachers. After the death of his father (in 1790), his brother Abdulkhaliq took over the business of trade. When he came to Bukhara for trading purposes, he met one of the famous sheikhs, Niyazkul Turkmani, and attended his meetings [2:18].

Shahobiddin ibn Bahaidin ibn Subhan ibn Abdulkarim al-Marjani (1818–1889) was a famous Kazan enlightener, philosopher and historical scholar. He was born on January 16, 1818 in the village of Yapancha near the city of Kazan. He initially studied at an old school. From the age of 15, Shahobiddin studied at a madrasah in the village of Tashkechuv, where his father, Bahaidin ibn Subhan Marjani, was a teacher, where he studied Persian and Arabic grammar under Mulla Badriddin Tusi.

After two years of study, his teachers recommended that he continue his education. Then, with his father's permission, in 1838, he went to Bukhara. The 20-year-old Marjani took a private room in one of the Bukhara madrasas and studied under such famous scholars as Salih Nadir Abdullah al-Khojandi, Muhammad Safar al-Khojandi, Domla Fazil al-Gijduvani, Abdulmumin al-Afshani, Khudoyberdi al-Baysuni, Baba Rafi' al-Khojandi, and Sharifata haji al-Bukhari. He continued his studies at the Kukaldash madrasa, where he studied under Mirza Salih al-Khojandi, one of the most famous scholars of Bukhara. Marjani independently studied in the libraries of Bukhara[2:22,23].

The Jadid movement also emerged in Turkestan, and in the second half of the 19th century, such enlightened figures as Abbasquli Oga Bakikhanov, Mirza Fatali Akhundov, Khoji Sayyid, Ashur Shirqawi, and Hasan Malikov Zardobi emerged. These intellectuals set themselves the goal of implementing reforms in the fields of education, the press, and theater, and achieved certain successes in this direction.

In conclusion, the Jadids who worked in Turkestan became the main propagandists of the national revival movement in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The Jadids' main focus was on developing the education system,

organizing the national press, and activating socio-political life. Jadids such as Muhammadkhodja Behbudiy, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdurauf Fitrat, Mahmudkhodja Behbudiy, Abdulla Avloniy sought to open new schools and introduce a modern education system. However, their reforms encountered certain obstacles. Many Jadids became victims of repression. Despite this, the Jadid movement made a significant contribution to the path of national revival and development in the Turkestan region.

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